

USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Dzhurayeva Feruza Abdumukhtorovna

Senior teacher of the Department of Uzbek language and social sciences of the Andijan Institute of Economics and Construction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10732549>

Abstract. *This article presents concepts such as the effective aspects of the use of information and communication technologies in educational institutions, the use and development of technologies, and the disclosure of all the possibilities of using multimedia technologies.*

Keywords: *hypermedia, multimedia, optical CDs, interactive web elements, individualization, differentiation, competent.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, great positive work has been carried out in higher and secondary special educational institutions in terms of introducing information and communication technologies (ICT), in particular, the use of multimedia technologies to enrich the content of the educational system, improve its organizational forms and quality. In recent years, great positive work has been carried out in higher and secondary special educational institutions in terms of introducing information and communication technologies (ICT), in particular, the use of multimedia technologies to enrich the content of the educational system, to improve its organizational forms and quality. The introduction of ICT into the teaching process of educational institutions serves as the main factor in increasing the effectiveness of education. Innovative technologies, including modern, advanced ICT, are being implemented in the educational system. In the process of education, teaching students and young people on the basis of technical tools and multimedia technologies, it is proven in practice that it helps the given knowledge to be quickly and easily assimilated, and that it is well understood and stored in memory. In addition, the possibility of organizing video conferences in the educational system is one of the achievements of the educational process. It is safe to say that this opportunity is an important factor in students' ability to exchange ideas, develop their free and creative thinking, and have the ability to convey their thoughts correctly and clearly. Through Internet systems, they get information about events, activities, news and achievements in the educational process in other countries of the world. It is known that multimedia technologies enrich the educational process, educational material makes it possible to improve the perception of educational information.

Multimedia is a visual and audio-effective interaction under the control of interactive software using modern technical and software tools, which combines text, sound, graphics, photos, and video in a single digital presentation method.

Hypermedia are computer files associated with hypertext media used in multimedia objects. Organization of education using computers and other Internet technologies, along with various advantages, there are also some disadvantages: it can be a problem with communication lines. These problems can be solved using optical compact discs called CD-ROM and DVD discs. The concept of multimedia means a set of tools that process information in various forms. Multimedia technologies are a set of tools that process information in various forms. Multimedia technologies primarily include sound and video processing tools. In addition, multiplication

(animation) and high-quality graphics are among multimedia technologies. Perhaps, in the future, multimedia tools will allow working with other types of information, for example, virtual reality. Modern educational tools - interactive, audio-visual, multimedia educational equipment - are not just tools that are becoming fashionable, but also a variable opportunity for the development of the personality of students. The task of the modern education system is not only to impart knowledge, but also to help students to develop their creative thinking. Any theoretical knowledge should be strengthened by practice. Therefore, in addition to the theoretical information provided by the teacher, practical, laboratory and project activities are required in the educational process. It is a factor that helps to form skills and abilities for independent research work and should be used throughout the entire educational activity. It is very important to actively involve and interest students in the educational process. The educational process is very effective on the basis of making teaching interesting and all students are fully active in it. Visual tools also play an important role in this, they develop the ability to work with different sources of information and compare the obtained results. As a result of the correct organization of the educational process, first of all, the universal effect of education, and based on it - useful qualifications and skills, and finally a wide range of potentials are formed. In the traditional teaching method of teachers, a lot of time is allocated for laboratory and practical work. This is a very important component of training specialists in the spirit of the times. It helps not only to strengthen the theoretical knowledge of the student, to increase the efficiency of mastering the educational material, but also to create practical skills in a specific field. However, we cannot say that such training will give a full-fledged result. The reason is that some laboratory equipment is not sufficient and laboratories and classrooms are not properly equipped with modern devices and equipment.

At the present time, when technologies are developing at a rapid pace, it is necessary to improve laboratories and stands for practical training every academic year. For this, it is necessary to consider additional costs. Another important factor is that, due to the slowness of the work or processes in some laboratory studies, learners find it difficult to repeat the analysis or experiments in the allotted time. Therefore, it is necessary to repeatedly repeat practical training in order to gain sufficient work skills and experience in a certain field. Unfortunately, in the conditions of traditional work, it is not always possible to achieve results due to the frequent breakdown of laboratory materials and equipment and the need for additional expenses. Based on the above, there is a need to introduce a new effective, universal pedagogical method that can help solve important tasks for the training of specialists. For this, it is necessary to ensure that classes in laboratory stands and educational workshops are not only interesting, but also convenient and easy for all students. Lessons should be able to attract, take into account all mental and didactic factors, demonstrate the processes in a lively way, increase the effectiveness of the training and learning of the taught subject, in general, the entire educational process, it is necessary to provide students with the opportunity to evaluate their acquired knowledge. From this point of view, the implementation of modern multimedia technologies helps to solve the above-mentioned tasks and to eliminate a number of shortcomings of the traditional teaching method. Currently, virtual stands are successfully used in higher and secondary special educational institutions. What is a virtual booth and how important is it in improving the effectiveness of education? A virtual stand is an educational practical stand or a training workshop, which helps to strengthen the theoretical knowledge of students, to create the necessary skills in a certain direction through computer programs and technologies. Virtual booths allow each student to "teach" their

own access to technology, monitor their knowledge. During laboratory work, the problem of understanding it in the necessary order and losing time related to others is eliminated due to the computer efficiency. It is especially important to save financial reserves. A modern CD-ROM can fit dozens, and sometimes hundreds, of lab tests. Now it is not difficult to calculate how cheap one such virtual laboratory stand will cost. In addition, together with them, educational institutions can be fully provided. Having an internet connection is even better. As a result of the introduction of virtual stands into the educational process, a higher quality of the educational process of training specialists is ensured compared to traditional education. This is achieved due to the use of specialized educational manuals consisting of an automated teacher and tester, systems, test tasks and questions for self-examination, rapid updating of the methodological basis of the educational process.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today's organizational forms of education, modern multimedia technologies and various necessary opportunities for education are available to us. The use of virtual stands in the educational process not only increases the quality and efficiency of education, reduces costs, but is also a factor in creating an environmentally friendly, safe environment. With the introduction of virtual stands, a different approach to educational content is required. With the help of multimedia stands, it becomes easier for students to remember any information not only by seeing, but also by hearing. The introduction of modern multimedia technologies into the educational process allows to achieve the following results compared to traditional education:

- enrichment of tables and pictures with color, sound, animations, hypertext;
- use of interactive web elements, tests;
- to enrich the theoretical material of the lesson;
- regular updating of information;
- more individual work with students in the educational process, increasing their interest in the lesson, supporting and developing their acquired knowledge;
- strengthening interdisciplinary relations in the educational process, comprehensive study of reality;
- to improve the flexibility, forms and methods of the educational process, technological base by introducing modern ICT tools. The use of multimedia tools in education provides the following opportunities:
 - ensuring the humanization of education;
 - increase the efficiency of the educational process;
 - development of the student's personal qualities (assimilation, thirst for knowledge, independent education, self-education, ability to improve oneself, creative abilities, applying acquired knowledge in practice ability, interest in learning, attitude to work);
 - development of the learner's communicative and social skills;
 - with the help of computer tools and information electronic educational resources, the possibilities of individualization and differentiation of open and distance education will be significantly expanded due to the separate (individual) education of each person;
 - looking at the learner as an active learning subject, recognizing his value;
 - taking into account the personal experience and individual characteristics of the learner;
 - conducting independent educational activities, in which the learner studies and develops independently;

• formation of skills in the use of modern educational technologies that help students to adapt to the current rapidly changing social conditions in order to successfully perform their professional tasks. The process of individual-oriented education with the help of multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multi-disciplinary, subject-oriented multimedia educational tools. They include a wide database, educational knowledge base, artificial intelligence systems, expert-tutoring systems, laboratory practices with the possibility of creating a mathematical model of the studied process and phenomena. According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education technology. Providing interactivity is one of the important achievements of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information. Interactivity refers to the provision of relevant information in accordance with the needs of the learner. Interactivity allows you to control the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings defined in the program, study the results, respond to the program's request about a specific desire of the user, set the speed of presentation of materials and the number of repetitions. But it is important to consider a number of aspects when using multimedia. Educational materials presented in multimedia should be easy to understand, provided with modern information and convenient tools.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to fully reveal all the possibilities of multimedia technologies and to use them effectively, students need the support of a potential (competent) teacher. As with the use of textbooks, in the use of multimedia tools, the educational strategy is enriched with content only when the teacher is engaged not only in providing information, but also in helping, supporting and guiding the learning process possible. Presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are usually more attractive than plain text and can complement the material being presented and provide the necessary emotional level. Multimedia tools can be used in harmony with different educational directions (styles) and can be used by people with different mental and age characteristics of learning and receiving knowledge: some learners directly and some like to learn and acquire knowledge by hearing and others by watching (video films). Interactive multimedia technologies provide non-traditional comfort to the learner with academic needs. In particular, it ensures the growth of phonological skills and reading skills of students with hearing impairment, as well as their visual acquisition of information. For those with speech and physical disabilities, it allows them to use the tools based on their individual needs. Multimedia tools are an effective and promising tool (instrument) of education, which provides the teacher with a large-scale array of information, rather than a traditional source of information; using not only text, graphics, schemes, but also sound, animations, video, etc. in a visual and harmonious way; creates an opportunity to select types of information in a sequence in accordance with the level of reception (perception) and logical learning of learners. In short, today multimedia technologies are one of the promising directions of informatization of the educational process. The introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process is an important condition for the intellectual development of students and pupils and the socio-economic development of our society. For this reason, today's teacher should work tirelessly on himself, possess the necessary qualities for his professional expertise as a person with broad creative thinking, who can effectively

use advanced pedagogical and multimedia technologies. The introduction of modern information technologies into the educational process requires the improvement of software and methodological support, the material base, as well as the improvement of the qualifications of teaching specialists. Multimedia tools are also important in improving the qualifications and skills of pedagogues.

REFERENCES

1. Abdumukhtarovna D. F. PURPOSE OF USING ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL LITERATURE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 312-315.
2. Djurayeva F. SCRATCH TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANIB ELEKTRON O ‘QUV ADABIYOTLARINI YARATISH IMKONIYATLARI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 5 Part 2. – С. 169-174.
3. Исаков Ж. А., Юрданидзе М. Х. Применение инновационных технологий на уроках черчения //Вестник науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 23-2 (77). – С. 21-24.
4. Исаков Ж. А., Мамиталиев А. Г., Уринбоев И. К. ТАСВИРИЙ САНЪАТ МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИДА ХАЛҚ АМАЛИЙ БЕЗАК САНЪАТИ РИВОЖИНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК МУАММОЛАРИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 601-605.
5. Z.T.Yunusova “Fizika fanini o`qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish” O`zbekistonda uchinchi renessans va innovatsion jarayonlar Hayot nashri 2023 yil 26 aprel, Andijon.